

Endmember Estimation with Maximum Distance Analysis

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Abstract—Endmember estimation plays a key role in hyperspectral imaging unmixing, often requiring the estimation of the number of endmembers and the extraction of their spectral signatures. However, most existing extraction algorithms require prior knowledge about the number of endmembers in the scene, being a critical process during unmixing. To bridge this, the new maximum distance analysis (MDA) method is proposed, which simultaneously estimates the number and the spectral signatures of endmembers without any prior information, being based on the assumption that endmembers form a simplex with the greatest volume over all pixel combinations. The simplex includes the farthest point from the coordinate origin in the spectral space, which implies that: 1) the farthest point from any other must be an endmember, 2) the farthest point from any line must be an endmember, and 3) the farthest point from any plane (or hyperplane) must be an endmember. Under this scenario, the farthest point from the coordinate origin is the first endmember, being used to create the aforementioned point, line, plane and hyperplane. The remaining endmembers are extracted by repetitively searching for the pixel points that satisfy the above three assumptions. The search for endmembers ends when the maximum distance between the pixel point and the hyperplane is zero. The number of endmembers is automatically determined by counting the pixel points that form the hyperplane. The proposed MDA method has been tested on synthetic and real data. The conducted experiments validate the effectiveness and efficiency of our method. Source code: <https://github.com/xuanwentao/Maximum-distance-analysis>

Index Terms—Hyperspectral image, spectral unmixing, maximum distance analysis, endmember extraction, endmember estimation.

I. INTRODUCTION

RE MOTELY sensed hyperspectral imaging (HSI) provides a significant amount of information about different materials on the Earth’s surface, capturing their reflectance behavior in the presence of solar radiation (which depends on their chemical composition and physical structure) by measuring the degree of absorption along the wavelengths of the electromagnetic spectrum (usually focused on the visible, near infrared -NIR- and shortwave infrared -SWIR- spectrum

[1]), in hundreds of narrow and continuous spectral bands [2]. As a result, each pixel contains the representation of a spectral signature, which is unique for each observed material. However, one typical problem associated with HSI data is its low spatial resolution, which inevitably leads to mixed pixels. Therefore, a mixed pixel covers several types of materials, which usually are composed of macroscopic objects such as water, soil, vegetation or buildings [3], being the corresponding spectrum a mixture of several ground cover spectra.

A challenge of the mixed pixel phenomenon is how to accurately identify the prime materials that compose it, determining the original spectral signatures and measuring the proportion in which they are present [4]. These principal constituent spectra are known as *endmembers*, and obtaining them is a hard and ill-posed problem where the reflectance pattern is (in general) not known *a priori*. Also, the sensor inaccuracies and atmospheric/light conditions (which introduce an important amount of noise into the spectra), and the high spectral-dimensionality hinders the endmember extraction task, due to the high intra-class variability and inter-class similarity of the data [5]. A significant technique for addressing this challenge is spectral unmixing [6]. In the available literature, spectral unmixing techniques [7]–[9] have been comprehensively investigated for the purpose of extracting endmembers and estimating their corresponding abundances, allowing the processing of HSI scenes at sub-pixel scale [10]. In fact, these techniques decompose each mixed pixel into a proportional composition of endmembers, where the constituent proportion with respect to different types of materials [11] for each pixel is defined as the abundance.

A significant challenge for existing spectral unmixing techniques is how to accurately extract endmembers [12]–[14] from remotely sensed HSI data. This is normally achieved by two seemingly independent but, in fact, highly correlated procedures: i) determining the number of endmembers, and ii) extracting their spectral signatures. As the accuracy of determining the number of endmembers has large influence on the endmember extraction step, both techniques can be considered as the overall procedure of endmember estimation.

In this paper, we propose a maximum distance analysis (MDA) method as a new unmixing framework that simultaneously counts and extracts endmembers without any prior information. To introduce the proposal in a detailed and comprehensive way, in subsection I-A we review the literature about estimating the number and extracting the signatures of endmembers, while in subsection I-B, we briefly describe

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the major contributions of our work in terms of presenting a new endmember estimation framework that simultaneously counts the number of endmembers and extracts their spectral signatures.

A. Literature Review

Estimating the number of endmembers is regarded as the first step of the endmember estimation task. The number of endmembers is often unavailable in an arbitrary HSI scene. In this scenario, most existing endmember extraction techniques cannot extract properly endmembers if the number of endmembers is not accurately determined. The limitation regarding an unknown number of endmembers hinders most existing endmember extraction techniques from an operational viewpoint. To address this limitation, several algorithms have been developed for counting the number of endmembers. Particularly, information theory-based algorithms, eigenvalue thresholding algorithms, and geometry characterization methods are three main families of techniques for estimating the number of endmembers. A brief summary of each family of methods is provided below.

- The first family includes some kind of criteria information, such as theoretic criteria based on minimum description length [15], [16], Akaike's information criterion [17], and Bayesian information criterion [18]. Furthermore, different models have been developed for encoding a negative data log-likelihood term and a penalty term. An accurate estimation of the number of endmembers is expected to be obtained when the model achieves a global optimum. These strategies rely on the empirical configuration of specific mixed models or likelihood functions, and improper configurations will cause estimation errors of the number of endmembers.
- The second family is related to a thresholding scheme, in which a threshold is applied to eigen-decomposition results from subspace analysis. Eigenvalue thresholding algorithms include principal component analysis (PCA) [19], hyperspectral signal subspace by minimum error (Hysime) [20], and the so-called Harsanyi-Farrand-Chang (HFC) method [21], coupled with its noise-whitened implementation (NWHFC) [22]. The PCA-based approaches aim to characterize a cutoff gap between the eigenvalues caused by signals and noise. However, these approaches will provide an incorrect estimation of the number of endmembers if the variation between the two eigenvalues is negligible. The Hysime approach conducts spectrum noise characterization and noise covariance estimation, and it requires high computational complexity. The HFC approach requires a fixed false alarm probability, which affects the estimated number of endmembers.
- Finally, the third family includes the geometry-based estimation of the number of endmembers (GENE), which includes the convex hull (GENE-CH) [23] algorithm and the affine hull (GENE-AH) [23] algorithm. Both the GENE-CH and the GENE-AH utilize data geometry and exploit the fact that all the observed pixel vectors should lie in the convex hull (CH) and affine hull (AH) of

the endmember signatures, respectively. Specially, the GENE algorithms operate along with an endmember extraction algorithm (EEA). In this scenario, a maximum hull volume would stop the EEA from extracting the next endmember signature. Therefore, the GENE algorithms depend on the effectiveness of the EEA used, and different endmember extraction algorithms (EEAs) introduce different accuracies when estimating the number of endmembers.

The subsequent step of endmember estimation is to extract endmembers (assuming that the number of endmembers has been previously determined). In the literature, N-FINDR algorithm and its derivatives are typical algorithms for extracting endmembers, and they include cofactor NFINDR [24], geometric distance constrained N-FINDR [25], and locality preserving N-FINDR [26]. The idea of N-FINDR algorithm (and its derivatives) is to search for a simplex with the greatest volume over all pixel combinations. The pixels that form the simplex are endmembers. N-FINDR algorithms need to repeatedly extract endmembers and randomly choose the initial endmember matrix. Simplex growing algorithm (SGA) [27] also randomly chooses an initial endmember to seek for an endmember convex geometry with minimum volume. To address the problem of repeatedly identifying an endmember, the automatic target generation process (ATGP) [28] is proposed to extract endmembers by considering the notion of orthogonal subspace projection (OSP). The alternating decoupled volume max-min (ADVMM) [29] and successive decoupled volume max-min (SDVMM) [29] are developed for addressing the worst-case simplex volume maximization problem by alternating optimization and by successive optimization, respectively. Specially, alternating volume maximization (AVMAX) [30] and successive volume maximization (SVMAX) [30] have been exploited to characterize more comprehensive criteria. The negative abundance-oriented (NABO) [31] algorithm uses the pixels lying outside the hypercone defined by a set of candidate endmembers as the best candidates. In this scenario, the accurate estimation of the number of endmembers is particularly significant for effective endmember extraction.

B. Contributions

As reviewed in Section I-A, most existing techniques for estimating the number of endmembers and extracting their signatures are performed as two independent procedures in the literature. Most EEAs require the prior knowledge about the number of endmembers, but the algorithms for counting endmembers tend to be characterized by independent methods that may not seamlessly benefit the EEAs. To bridge these two seemingly independent procedures (but in fact highly related procedures), we introduce a maximum distance analysis (MDA) method to simultaneously count and extract endmembers as a single, overall procedure to endmember estimation. The major contributions of this paper can be outlined as follows:

- 1) The proposed MDA method completes the overall endmember estimation task, i.e., determining the number of endmembers and extracting their spectral signatures.

Fig. 1. Schematic diagram illustrating how to extract an endmember (from two previously available ones) by using our MDA method. The farthest pixel point from the line $L_{\{AB\}}$ is the third endmember. The red dots represent endmembers that have been previously extracted, and the blue dots denote the pixel points in the pixel space.

- 2) The proposed MDA method only involves vector operations, keeping its computational complexity very low.
- 3) The proposed MDA method exhibits robust performance to noise.

C. Paper Outline

The rest of the paper is organized as follows. Section II introduces the proposed endmember estimation method, explaining how the method can automatically extract endmembers and discussing a stopping criterion and how to utilize it to count the number of endmembers. Section III provides an empirical evaluation of the effectiveness and efficiency reached by the MDA method in counting and extracting endmembers on synthetic data and real data. Finally, section IV concludes this paper with some remarks and hints at plausible future research lines.

II. PROPOSED METHOD

A. Extracting endmember signatures

Let $\mathbf{X} = [\mathbf{x}_1, \mathbf{x}_2, \dots, \mathbf{x}_i, \dots, \mathbf{x}_N] \in \mathbb{R}^{L \times N}$ denote a HSI dataset with L bands and N pixels, where the n th pixel $\mathbf{x}_i = [x_{1i}, x_{2i}, \dots, x_{Li}]^T \in \mathbb{R}^{L \times 1}$ represents an L -dimensional vector. From a geometric point of view, we know that endmembers are supposed to form a simplex with the greatest volume over all pixel combinations, and they are distributed at the outermost region of all pixels to enclose them. Therefore, if one pixel point is a candidate to be an endmember, it must satisfy two conditions: 1) the pixel point is an essential component of the simplex with the greatest volume over all pixel combinations, and 2) the pixel point is distributed in the outermost region of all pixels. Some EEAs utilize the idea of a simplex to search for some pixel points far away from each other as endmembers, and the operations inevitably render considerable computational overloads and make EEAs inefficient for tackling large-size remote sensing HSI scenes. To address this problem, we give some definitions regarding distances to effectively and efficiently extract endmembers, where the task of extracting endmembers does not require prior knowledge about the number of endmembers.

Definition 1. We define the farthest pixel point from the coordinate origin in the pixel space as the first endmember.

Fig. 2. Schematic diagram illustrating how to extract an endmember (from three previously available ones) by using our MDA method. The farthest pixel point from the plane $P_{\{ABC\}}$ is the fourth endmember.

The distance d_{ij} between the i th and j th hyperspectral pixel points in the pixel space is computed by the Euclidean distance

$$d_{ij} = \|\mathbf{x}_i - \mathbf{x}_j\|_2 = \sqrt{(x_{1i} - x_{1j})^2 + \dots + (x_{Li} - x_{Lj})^2} \quad (1)$$

We compute the distances between each pixel point and the coordinate origin by using Eq. (1) to get the farthest pixel point from the coordinate origin, computing as a result of the first endmember. In this sense, this first point will easily satisfy the two conditions to be an endmember.

Definition 2. We define the farthest pixel point from the first extracted endmember as the second endmember.

We compute the distances between each pixel point and the first extracted endmember through Eq. (1) to get the farthest pixel point from the first endmember, getting as a result the second endmember. We observe that the second extracted endmember also satisfies the two conditions to be considered as endmember.

Definition 3. We define the farthest pixel point from the line defined by the first and second extracted endmembers as the third endmember.

Assuming that we have acquired the first endmember A and the second endmember B, as shown in Fig. 1, we can compute the distance $d_{i-L_{\{AB\}}}$ between any pixel point i and the line $L_{\{AB\}}$ to get the third endmember. Then, the angle α between vectors \vec{Bi} and \vec{BA} is trigonometrically computed by Eq. (2)

$$\alpha = \arccos \frac{\vec{Bi} \cdot \vec{BA}}{\|\vec{Bi}\|_2 \|\vec{BA}\|_2} \quad (2)$$

As shown in Fig. 1, the distance $d_{i-L_{\{AB\}}}$ between any pixel point i and the line $L_{\{AB\}}$ is computed by

$$d_{i-L_{\{AB\}}} = \|\vec{Bi}\|_2 \sin \alpha \quad (3)$$

In this sense, we can obtain the index e_3 of the third endmember by maximizing the distance with

$$e_3 = \arg \max_{i \in \{1, 2, \dots, N\}} d_{i-L_{\{AB\}}} \quad (4)$$

and we use the index e_3 to extract the third endmember C. Moreover, the third extracted endmember also satisfies the two conditions in order to be considered as an endmember.

Fig. 3. Step-by-step process illustrating how to extract four endmembers using the MDA method.

Definition 4. We define the farthest point from the plane formed by the first, second and third extracted endmembers as the fourth endmember.

Assuming that the three extracted endmembers A, B and C form a plane $P_{\{ABC\}}$, as shown in Fig. 2, we compute the distance $d_{i_{P_{\{ABC\}}}}$ between any pixel point i and the plane $P_{\{ABC\}}$ to get the fourth endmember. Assuming that O is the coordinate origin in the pixel space and \mathbf{n} is the normal vector of the plane $P_{\{ABC\}}$, we have the expressions

$$\begin{aligned} \vec{AB} \cdot \mathbf{n} &= 0; \\ \vec{BC} \cdot \mathbf{n} &= 0; \\ \vec{AC} \cdot \mathbf{n} &= 0; \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} \vec{AB} &= \vec{OB} - \vec{OA}; \\ \vec{BC} &= \vec{OC} - \vec{OB}; \\ \vec{AC} &= \vec{OC} - \vec{OA}; \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

Based on Eq. (5) and (6), we know

$$\begin{aligned} \vec{AB} \cdot \mathbf{n} &= (\vec{OB} - \vec{OA}) \cdot \mathbf{n} = 0; \\ \vec{BC} \cdot \mathbf{n} &= (\vec{OC} - \vec{OB}) \cdot \mathbf{n} = 0; \\ \vec{AC} \cdot \mathbf{n} &= (\vec{OC} - \vec{OA}) \cdot \mathbf{n} = 0; \end{aligned}$$

Because $\mathbf{n} \neq \mathbf{0}$, $\vec{OA} \neq \mathbf{0}$, $\vec{OB} \neq \mathbf{0}$ and $\vec{OC} \neq \mathbf{0}$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \vec{OA} \cdot \mathbf{n} &= 0; \\ \vec{OB} \cdot \mathbf{n} &= 0; \\ \vec{OC} \cdot \mathbf{n} &= 0; \end{aligned}$$

Then, we can define matrix $\mathbf{X}_3 = [\vec{OA}, \vec{OB}, \vec{OC}] \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times 3}$, where N is the number of pixels. We get the normal vector \mathbf{n} by addressing

$$\mathbf{X}_3^T \mathbf{n} = \mathbf{0} \quad (7)$$

The angle β between vectors \vec{Bi} and \mathbf{n} is trigonometrically computed by

$$\beta = \arccos \frac{\vec{Bi} \cdot \mathbf{n}}{\|\vec{Bi}\|_2 \|\mathbf{n}\|_2} \quad (8)$$

Therefore, the distance $d_{i_{P_{\{ABC\}}}}$ is computed by

$$d_{i_{P_{\{ABC\}}}} = \|\vec{Bi}\|_2 |\cos \beta| \quad (9)$$

where symbol $|\cdot|$ denotes the absolute value of $\cos \beta$. With this, we can obtain the index e_4 of the fourth endmember by

$$e_4 = \arg \max_{i \in \{1, 2, \dots, N\}} d_{i_{P_{\{ABC\}}}} \quad (10)$$

Finally the index e_4 is used to extract the fourth endmember D, which also satisfies the two conditions to be considered as an endmember. Fig. 3 shows graphically the process of extracting four endmembers.

Definition 5. We define the farthest point from the hyperplane $P_{\{ABCD \dots\}}$ formed by all extracted endmembers $\{A, B, C, D, \dots\}$ as the next endmember.

Fig. 4. Performance of endmember extraction from synthetic hyperspectral data with pure pixels for each type of material

Assuming that we have extracted endmembers $\{ABCD\dots\}$, and these endmembers form a hyperplane $P_{\{ABCD\dots\}}$. We have the matrix $\mathbf{X}_{\{ABCD\dots\}} = \{\overrightarrow{OA}, \overrightarrow{OB}, \overrightarrow{OC}, \overrightarrow{OD}, \dots\} \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times E}$, where N is the number of pixels and E is the number of endmembers that have been extracted. Assuming that \mathbf{w} is the normal vector of the hyperplane $P_{\{ABCD\dots\}}$ and b is the offset or distance between coordinate origin and the hyperplane, we compute the normal vector \mathbf{w} by

$$\mathbf{X}_{\{ABCD\dots\}}^T \mathbf{w} = \mathbf{0} \quad (11)$$

\mathbf{x} is a pixel point of the hyperplane $P_{\{ABCD\dots\}}$, and the

hyperplane can be written as Eq. (12)

$$\mathbf{w}^T \mathbf{x} + b = 0 \quad (12)$$

In this context, there is a pixel point $\mathbf{x}_i(\vec{x}_i)$, whose distance between it and the hyperplane is denoted as d . Also, we consider point $\mathbf{x}_j(\vec{x}_j)$ as the projection of \mathbf{x}_i onto the hyperplane, where γ is the angle between vectors \mathbf{w} and $\vec{x}_i \vec{x}_j$, $\cos \gamma = 1$, and we have

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{w}^T \vec{x}_j \vec{x}_i &= w^1(x_i^1 - x_j^1) + w^2(x_i^2 - x_j^2) + \dots + w^N(x_i^N - x_j^N) \\ &= w^1 x_i^1 + w^2 x_i^2 + \dots + w^N x_i^N \\ &\quad - (w^1 x_j^1 + w^2 x_j^2 + \dots + w^N x_j^N) \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

Fig. 5. Performance of endmember extraction from synthetic hyperspectral data with no pure pixels for each type of material.

and

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{w} \cdot \vec{x}_i \vec{x}_j &= \|\mathbf{w}\|_2 \|\vec{x}_i \vec{x}_j\|_2 \cos \gamma \\
 &= \|\mathbf{w}\|_2 \|\vec{x}_i \vec{x}_j\|_2 \\
 &= \|\mathbf{w}\|_2 d
 \end{aligned} \tag{14}$$

and also

$$|\mathbf{w} \cdot \vec{x}_i \vec{x}_j| = \|\mathbf{w}\|_2 d \tag{15}$$

We know $\mathbf{w}^T \vec{x}_j = -b$ from Eq. (12) and the Eq. (13) is represented as

$$\mathbf{w}^T \vec{x}_j \vec{x}_i = w^1 x_i^1 + w^2 x_i^2 + \dots + w^N x_i^N - (-b) \tag{16}$$

Based on the equations (15) and (16), we have

$$\begin{aligned}
 \|\mathbf{w}\|_2 d &= |w^1 x_i^1 + w^2 x_i^2 + \dots + w^N x_i^N + b| \\
 &= |\mathbf{w}^T \vec{x}_i + b|
 \end{aligned} \tag{17}$$

Therefore, the distance between any point \vec{x}_i and the considered hyperplane is computed by

$$d = \frac{|\mathbf{w}^T \vec{x}_i + b|}{\|\mathbf{w}\|_2} \tag{18}$$

Specially, support vector machines (SVMs) [32] provide the distance calculation given by Eq. (18) between any point

Fig. 6. Performance of endmember extraction from synthetic hyperspectral data with different noise levels: (a)-(c) SNR=10dB; (d)-(f) SNR=15dB; (g)-(i) SNR=20dB; (k)-(l) SNR=25dB.

Fig. 7. Performance of estimating the number of endmembers in: (a) synthetic hyperspectral data with pure pixels for each type of material; (b) synthetic hyperspectral data with no pure pixels for each type of material; (c) synthetic hyperspectral data with noise.

TABLE I
RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN THE NUMBER OF ENDMEMBERS AND THE MAXIMUM DISTANCE ON DIFFERENT SYNTHETIC DATA SETS.

Actual number of endmembers	Estimated number of endmembers + the maximum distance			
	synthetic data with pure pixels		synthetic data with no pure pixels	
4	4 + 0.2176	5 + 0	4 + 0.0835	5 + 0
5	5 + 0.1066	6 + 0	5 + 0.0478	6 + 0
6	6 + 0.0126	7 + 0	6 + 0.0106	7 + 0
7	7 + 0.0328	8 + 0	7 + 0.0045	8 + 0
8	8 + 0.0305	9 + 0	8 + 0.0054	9 + 0
9	9 + 0.0249	10 + 0	9 + 0.0119	10 + 0
10	10 + 0.0844	11 + 0	10 + 0.0289	11 + 0
11	11 + 0.0301	12 + 0	11 + 0.0056	12 + 0
12	12 + 0.0233	13 + 0	12 + 0.0077	13 + 0
13	13 + 0.0162	14 + 0	13 + 0.0038	14 + 0
14	14 + 0.0054	15 + 0	14 + 0.0032	15 + 0
15	15 + 0.0015	16 + 0	15 + 3.61e ⁻⁰⁴	16 + 0
16	16 + 6.43e ⁻⁰⁴	17 + 0	16 + 0.0014	17 + 0
17	17 + 0.0017	18 + 0	17 + 9.98e ⁻⁰⁵	18 + 0
18	18 + 0.002	19 + 0	18 + 0.0011	19 + 0
19	19 + 9.56e ⁻⁰⁴	20 + 0	19 + 0.0011	20 + 0
20	20 + 0.002	21 + 0	20 + 9.47e ⁻⁰⁴	21 + 0
21	21 + 0.0013	22 + 0	21 + 3.48e ⁻⁰⁴	22 + 0
22	22 + 0.0065	23 + 0	22 + 0.0022	23 + 0
23	23 + 0.0089	24 + 0	23 + 0.003	24 + 0
24	24 + 0.0028	25 + 0	24 + 0.003	25 + 0
25	25 + 3.38e ⁻⁰⁴	26 + 0	25 + 0.001	26 + 0

\vec{x}_i and the hyperplane. We can get the index of the next endmember by

$$\hat{e} = \arg \max_{i \in \{1, 2, \dots, N\}} \frac{|\mathbf{w}^T \vec{x}_i + b|}{\|\mathbf{w}\|_2} \quad (19)$$

We then use the index \hat{e} to extract the next endmember, which also satisfies the aforementioned two conditions that any point must meet in order to be considered an endmember.

B. Estimating the number of endmembers

From the mathematical discussions in the previous subsection, we know that: 1) if one pixel point belongs to one hyperplane, the distance between it and the hyperplane is zero,

and 2) if one point does not belong to one hyperplane, the distance between it and the hyperplane is greater than zero. Based on the aforementioned concepts, we give the following definition as the stopping criterion for endmember extraction, obtaining also the final number of endmembers by counting those points that have been extracted as endmembers.

Definition 6. *The stopping criterion for endmember extraction is that the maximum distances between the pixel point and the hyperplane formed by the extracted endmember is zero. Simultaneously, the number of endmembers is determined by counting the number of candidate points that have been extracted.*

TABLE II

RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN THE NUMBER OF ENDMEMBERS AND THE MAXIMUM DISTANCE ON SYNTHETIC DATA WITH DIFFERENT NOISE LEVELS.

Actual number of endmembers	Estimated number of endmembers + the maximum distance							
	SNR = 10dB		SNR = 15dB		SNR = 20dB		SNR = 25dB	
5	5 + 0.098	6 + 0	5 + 0.1085	6 + 0	5 + 0.0287	6 + 0	5 + 0.1083	6 + 0
10	10 + 9.67e ⁻⁰⁴	11 + 0	10 + 0.0091	11 + 0	10 + 0.0082	11 + 0	10 + 0.0469	11 + 0
15	15 + 0.0695	16 + 0	15 + 0.0051	16 + 0	15 + 0.0036	16 + 0	15 + 0.0184	16 + 0
20	20 + 0.035	21 + 0	20 + 0.037	21 + 0	20 + 0.0383	21 + 0	20 + 0.0044	21 + 0
25	25 + 0.0386	26 + 0	25 + 0.0268	26 + 0	25 + 0.0037	26 + 0	25 + 0.0172	26 + 0

To conclude this section, we emphasize that our MDA method can extract endmembers without any previous knowledge about the number of endmembers, since it can perform both endmember extraction and estimation of the number of endmembers.

III. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

We use both synthetic and real hyperspectral data to evaluate the performance of the MDA method in the tasks of estimating the number of endmembers and extracting their signatures. Specifically, we conduct a series of experiments to demonstrate the effectiveness and efficiency of our newly proposed MDA method in two different tasks. The endmember extraction capacity of our method is assessed with that of eight other methods, i.e., alternating decoupled volume max-min (ADVMM) [29], successive decoupled volume max-min (SDVMM) [29], alternating volume maximization (AVMAX) [30] and successive volume maximization (SVMAX) [30], p-norm-based pure pixel identification (TRIP) [23], automatic target generation process (ATGP) [28], negative abundance-oriented (NABO) [31], and simplex growing algorithm (SGA) [27]. Additionally, the accuracy of our method in the task of estimating the number of endmembers is assessed with that of the hyperspectral signal subspace by minimum error (Hysime) [20], Harsanyi-Farrand-Chang (HFC) [21] and geometry-based estimation of number of endmembers-affine hull (GENE-AH) [23] methods. We use three metrics to evaluate the accuracy of the different tested methods: spectral information divergence (SID), abundance information divergence (AID), and root mean square error (RMSE). Let $\mathbf{X}_e = [\mathbf{x}_1, \mathbf{x}_2, \dots, \mathbf{x}_m, \dots, \mathbf{x}_M] \in \mathbb{R}^{L \times M}$ denote the true endmember signatures and $\hat{\mathbf{X}} = [\hat{\mathbf{x}}_1, \hat{\mathbf{x}}_2, \dots, \hat{\mathbf{x}}_m, \dots, \hat{\mathbf{x}}_M] \in \mathbb{R}^{L \times M}$ the estimated endmember signatures, where M is the number of endmembers, $\mathbf{x}_m = [x_{1m}, x_{2m}, \dots, x_{lm}, \dots, x_{Lm}]^T \in \mathbb{R}^{L \times 1}$, and $\hat{\mathbf{x}}_m = [\hat{x}_{1m}, \hat{x}_{2m}, \dots, \hat{x}_{lm}, \dots, \hat{x}_{Lm}]^T \in \mathbb{R}^{L \times 1}$. The probability distribution vector of the m th endmember signature is given by

$$\mathbf{p}_m = \frac{\mathbf{x}_m}{\sum_{l=1}^L x_{lm}} \quad (20)$$

The vector characterizes the variability of spectral signatures. In this sense, let $\mathbf{P}_e = [\mathbf{p}_1, \mathbf{p}_2, \dots, \mathbf{p}_m, \dots, \mathbf{p}_M] \in \mathbb{R}^{L \times M}$

be the probability distribution matrix for $\hat{\mathbf{X}}_e$, while $\hat{\mathbf{P}} = [\hat{\mathbf{p}}_1, \hat{\mathbf{p}}_2, \dots, \hat{\mathbf{p}}_m, \dots, \hat{\mathbf{p}}_M] \in \mathbb{R}^{L \times M}$ represents the probability distribution matrix for \mathbf{X}_e . Also, let p_{lm} be the (i, j) th element of matrix \mathbf{P}_e , and \hat{p}_{lm} be the (i, j) th element of matrix $\hat{\mathbf{P}}$. We have the following equation

$$D(\mathbf{x}_m | \hat{\mathbf{x}}_m) = \sum_{l=1}^L p_{lm} \log \frac{p_{lm}}{\hat{p}_{lm}}. \quad (21)$$

The relative entropy between \mathbf{X}_e and $\hat{\mathbf{X}}$ is measured as $D(\mathbf{X}_e | \hat{\mathbf{X}}) = [D(\mathbf{x}_1 | \hat{\mathbf{x}}_1), D(\mathbf{x}_2 | \hat{\mathbf{x}}_2), \dots, D(\mathbf{x}_M | \hat{\mathbf{x}}_M)] \in \mathbb{R}^{1 \times M}$. The relative entropy is asymmetric with respect to \mathbf{X}_e and $\hat{\mathbf{X}}$. To render a symmetric metric based on the relative entropy, the spectral information divergence (SID) [33] given by Eq. (22) has been considered.

$$\text{SID} = D(\mathbf{X}_e | \hat{\mathbf{X}}) + D(\hat{\mathbf{X}} | \mathbf{X}_e). \quad (22)$$

In order to make a fair comparison based on more comprehensive metrics, the abundance $\hat{\mathbf{a}}$ for one pixel \mathbf{x} with respect to the estimated endmembers $\hat{\mathbf{X}}$ is employed, where each element of $\hat{\mathbf{a}} = [\hat{a}_1, \hat{a}_2, \dots, \hat{a}_M]^T \in \mathbb{R}^{M \times 1}$ represents the abundance with respect to one endmember. Let also $\mathbf{q} \in \mathbb{R}^{L \times 1}$ denote additive noise. The abundance in terms of a linear mixture model [34] is given as follows

$$\mathbf{x} = \hat{\mathbf{X}}\hat{\mathbf{a}} + \mathbf{q}. \quad (23)$$

subject to the nonnegative and sum-to-one constraints

$$\hat{a}_m \geq 0, \quad m = 1, 2, \dots, M; \quad \sum_{m=1}^M \hat{a}_m = 1. \quad (24)$$

The abundance vectors are used to replace the endmember signatures in SID to derive more comprehensive metrics. Let $\mathbf{A}_e = [\mathbf{a}_1, \mathbf{a}_2, \dots, \mathbf{a}_n, \dots, \mathbf{a}_N] \in \mathbb{R}^{M \times N}$ denote the true endmember abundance and $\hat{\mathbf{A}} = [\hat{\mathbf{a}}_1, \hat{\mathbf{a}}_2, \dots, \hat{\mathbf{a}}_n, \dots, \hat{\mathbf{a}}_N] \in \mathbb{R}^{M \times N}$ be the estimated endmember abundance. Accordingly, the abundance information divergence (AID) is given as follows

$$\text{AID} = D(\mathbf{A}_e | \hat{\mathbf{A}}) + D(\hat{\mathbf{A}} | \mathbf{A}_e). \quad (25)$$

TABLE III
AVERAGE RUNNING TIME (SECONDS) FOR THE TASK OF EXTRACTING ENDMEMBERS FROM DIFFERENT SYNTHETIC DATA SETS.

Synthetic data	Methods								
	SDVMM	ADVMM	AVMAX	SVMAX	TRIP	ATGP	NABO	SGA	Our method
With pure pixels	1.2179	1.1892	1.1921	1.1296	1.0602	0.9673	0.8356	1.1021	1.0535
With no pure pixels	1.4606	1.5220	1.4432	1.3318	1.3223	1.4270	1.0935	1.6298	1.2829
With 10dB noise	1.5179	1.5384	1.4853	1.4039	1.4253	1.2495	1.4616	1.1283	1.1702
With 15dB noise	1.5120	1.5747	1.4695	1.4348	1.4236	1.3104	1.4792	1.1463	1.1797
With 20dB noise	1.6468	1.7343	1.6237	1.5999	1.5910	1.3606	1.6055	1.2940	1.2392
With 25dB noise	1.5132	1.6649	1.5289	1.4345	1.4711	1.2931	1.5003	1.2091	1.2159

TABLE IV
AVERAGE RUNNING TIME (SECONDS) FOR THE TASK OF ESTIMATING THE NUMBER OF ENDMEMBERS IN DIFFERENT SYNTHETIC DATA SETS.

Synthetic data	Methods			
	Hysime	HFC	GENE-AH	Our method
With pure pixels	0.1629	0.0928	5.3545	1.0535
With no pure pixels	0.1548	0.0631	5.3363	1.2829
With 10dB noise	0.1481	0.0670	5.9337	1.1702
With 15dB noise	0.1539	0.0680	6.0469	1.1797
With 20dB noise	0.1648	0.0719	6.3767	1.2392
With 25dB noise	0.1477	0.0681	6.0306	1.2159

The matrix \mathbf{R} is defined as $(\mathbf{A}_e - \hat{\mathbf{A}})$, where each R_{ij} is the (i, j) th element of the matrix \mathbf{R} . The root mean square error (RMSE) is given as follows

$$\text{RMSE} = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{i=1}^N \sum_{j=1}^M R_{ij}^2}{NM}}. \quad (26)$$

EEAs get the most accurate results when the values of the above three metrics SID, AID and RMSE are zero.

A. Synthetic data

The synthetic data are created based on the United States Geological Survey (USGS) mineral spectra library¹. We generate synthetic data partially based on the linear mixture method proposed by Miao *et al.* [35]. Based on the linear mixture model, we simulate three different types of synthetic data: a) synthetic data with pure pixels for each type of material, b) synthetic data with no pure pixels for each type of material, and c) synthetic data with different levels of noise.

We utilize Definitions 1 to 6 to extract the signatures and estimate the number of endmembers. For simplicity, we summarize below the steps conducted for extracting and counting endmembers with our MDA method:

- 1) We calculate the distances between *every pixel point and coordinate origin* in the pixel space and extract the pixel point with the maximum distance as the first endmember.
- 2) We calculate the distances between *every pixel point and the first extracted endmember* in the pixel space and extract the pixel point with the maximum distance as the second endmember.
- 3) We calculate the distance between *every pixel point and the line* defined by the first and second extracted endmembers, extracting the pixel point with the maximum distance as the third endmember.
- 4) We calculate the distance between *every pixel point and the plane* formed by the first, second and third extracted endmembers, extracting the pixel point with the maximum distance as the fourth endmember.
- 5) We calculate the distance between *every pixel point and the hyperplane* formed by all the previously extracted endmembers, extracting the pixel point with the maximum distance as the next endmember.
- 6) We finish endmember extraction procedure when the *maximum distance* between the pixel point and the hyperplane formed by all the previously extracted endmembers is *zero*. Simultaneously, we determine the number of endmembers by counting the number of points that have been extracted.

1) *Effectiveness Evaluation:* We employ the aforementioned three metrics (particularly, SID, AID and RMSE) to evaluate the performance of the proposed MDA method in extracting endmembers on synthetic data with and without pure pixels for each type of material. The value of zero indicates the best performance in terms of the considered metrics. Figs. 4 and 5 illustrate the accuracy of different methods in extracting endmembers from different synthetic data sets. From Fig. 4, we can observe that the values of SID, AID and RMSE are almost close to zero for the eight

¹<https://speclab.cr.usgs.gov/spectral-lib.html>

TABLE V
PERFORMANCE AND PROCESSING TIME (SECONDS) FOR DIFFERENT ENDMEMBER EXTRACTION ALGORITHMS APPLIED TO THE SAMSON SUBIMAGE

Metrics	Methods								
	SDVMM	ADVMM	AVMAX	SVMAX	TRIP	ATGP	NABO	SGA	Our method
SID	0.0274	0.0270	0.0279	0.0277	0.0201	1.0830	0.0297	1.8300	0.0194
AID	13.8716	13.8714	13.8701	13.8744	13.9172	14.9989	13.3491	14.9989	13.4083
RMSE	0.4028	0.4033	0.4032	0.4028	0.4027	0.2572	0.4033	0.2572	0.4025
Time (seconds)	1.9102	1.8278	1.7307	1.7074	1.8250	1.6142	1.5294	1.7675	1.4766

Fig. 8. False color composition of the considered Samson subimage.

compared methods, with the NABO exhibits a significant error when the number of endmembers is six on the synthetic data with pure pixels. From Fig. 5, we see that all methods get almost same results in terms of SID, AID and RMSE.

We also employ SID, AID and RMSE to evaluate the performance of the proposed MDA method in extracting endmembers from synthetic data with different noise levels (10dB, 15dB, 20dB and 25dB). In this sense, the number of considered endmembers has been set to 5, 10, 15, 20 and 25. Fig. 6 displays the results for the three considered metrics obtained by different methods. From Fig. 6, we can see that the values of SID, AID and RMSE are in general close to zero, and this reflects the fact that the MDA method exhibits good and robust behaviour with different noise levels, achieving accurate results in terms of extracting endmembers.

To evaluate the performance of the proposed MDA method in the task of estimating the number of endmembers, we utilize Definition 6. Table I presents the relationship between the estimated and actual number of endmembers and the maximum distance on synthetic data sets with and without pure pixels for each type of material. Moreover, Table II presents the relationship between the estimated and actual number of endmembers and the maximum distance on synthetic data sets with different noise levels. From Table I and Table II, we can see that the maximum distance is zero when the estimated number of endmembers exceeds the actual number of endmembers on different synthetic data sets. Therefore, the proposed MDA method provides accurate estimations about the number of endmembers on different synthetic data sets.

Specially, Table II also reflects that the proposed MDA method exhibits robustness to different noise levels when estimating the number of endmembers.

We applied Hysime, HFC and GENE-AH as comparison methods to evaluate the performance of the proposed MDA method in estimating the number of endmembers in different synthetic data sets. Fig. 7 displays the number of endmembers determined by different methods on different synthetic data sets. From Fig. 7(a) and 7(b), it can be observed that the MDA method and other two traditional methods (HFC and GENE-AH) achieve accurate estimations about the number of endmembers, while the Hysime method has errors after the number of endmembers is 17 (and 14) on the synthetic data sets with (and without) pure pixels, respectively. From Fig. 7(c), we can observe that Hysime, HFC and the proposed MDA method can estimate the number of endmembers efficiently, and GENE-AH leads to small errors when counting the number of endmembers.

2) *Computational Efficiency Evaluation:* Once the effectiveness of the proposed MDA method has been evaluated in Section III-A, we will evaluate the computational efficiency of different methods in the tasks of extracting the number and signatures of endmembers from different synthetic data sets.

Table III reports the average running time of different methods in the task of extracting endmembers from different synthetic data sets. From Table III, we can see that all eight considered methods and the proposed MDA method are very fast. Although the proposed MDA method is not the fastest, the time gap between different methods is very small. Specially, the eight considered methods only performs the task of extracting endmembers, while the proposed MDA method performs two tasks, i.e., extracting and counting the number of endmembers. In this scenario, our proposed MDA method has a certain advantage in terms of the overall endmember estimation procedure, i.e., it can both extract and count endmembers quite fast.

Table IV presents the average running time of different methods in estimating the number of endmembers in different synthetic data sets. From Table IV, we can conclude that, on the one hand, the efficiency of Hysime, HFC and the proposed MDA method are very high and the time gap between them is very small, while on the other hand the efficiency of GENE-AH method is a bit lower. Similarly, Hysime, HFC and GENE-

Fig. 9. Reference signatures and estimated endmember signatures by the proposed MDA method from the Samson subimage.

AH methods only perform the estimation of the number of endmembers, while the proposed MDA method performs two tasks, i.e., extracting and counting endmembers.

B. Real data

We utilize the Samson real hyperspectral image² to evaluate the performance of the proposed MDA method in extracting endmembers. The Samson data comprises 952×952 pixels, each of which has 156 bands covering the wavelength range from 401 to 889 nm. The original image is quite large, leading to high computational cost for several of the considered algorithms. In this experiment, a subimage with 95×95 pixels is used. The spatial coordinates of the first pixel of the subimage in the full Samson image is (252,332). The Samson data contains three endmembers, i.e., tree, water and soil (a false color composite of the considered subimage is shown in Fig. 8).

We employ SID, AID and RMSE to evaluate the performance of the proposed MDA (as compared to other state-of-the-art methods) in the task of extracting endmembers from the Samson data. Table V shows the performance metrics of different methods applied to the Samson subimage, together with the processing time (in seconds) for each method. From Table V, we can conclude that our method exhibits very low values in terms of SID, AID and RMSE. Although our method is not always the best for each considered metric, it is always among the best algorithms in each case. Most importantly, our method is the fastest, according to the measured processing times. This reveals that our method can extract endmembers effectively and efficiently from real data.

Fig. 9 shows a qualitative comparison between the endmembers extracted with the proposed MDA method from the Samson subimage and their corresponding reference (ground-truth) signatures. From Fig. 9, we can conclude that the endmember signatures estimated by the proposed MDA method are in very good spectral agreement with the reference signatures. The results shown in Fig. 9 suggest the high accuracy of the proposed MDA method in extracting endmembers from real data.

IV. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

We have developed a new algorithm for estimating the number of endmembers and the corresponding endmember signatures, referred to as maximum distance analysis (MDA). Our MDA method can extract endmember signatures without any prior knowledge about the number of endmembers. The MDA method has been validated using synthetic data and real data, and shown to be able of accurately performing both endmember extraction and counting, exhibiting very high efficiency in comparison with other traditional unmixing methods.

As with any new approach, there are still some unresolved issues that may present challenges over time. Specifically, the distance calculation in our proposed method may need to be adapted if the hyperspectral data are nonlinearly mixed. Further experiments with more hyperspectral real data sets should be conducted to fully substantiate the validity of our approach.

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²<http://lesun.weebly.com/hyperspectral-data-set.html>

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